

Integration of Digital Platforms in Modern Human Resource and Talent Management

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ABSTRACT: Technologies give opportunities to make smarter decisions about talents based on data and people analytics platforms. Corporations can kick start their transformational change to build momentum by embracing a bionic strategy that combines human and technical capabilities. There are varieties of different IT companies offering their platforms for personnel management. The purpose of this article is to investigate digitalization and its impact on talent management in a continuously digitalized business environment. The paper analyzes related studies on talent management and different aspects in managing people in a highly digitalized working environment using an extensive literature review of recent quantitative and qualitative papers from diverse sectors.

KEYWORDS: Talent management; human resource management; employee platform; digital platform.

INTRODUCTION

The present global environment has forced the digitization of data, which can now be reached through a wide range of electronic platforms. In order to preserve a competitive advantage in the era of digital transformation, firms have been pushed to acquire and nurture talent to reduce the misalignment between employees and occupations. Dorasamy, N. (2021) states: "This has profoundly shifted the dynamics of traditional human resource management toward not only all the functional areas of human resources being virtualized such as e-recruitment, e-selection, e-performance, e-employee development and e-evaluation, but also managing talent through interconnected and integrated elements of human resource management across the entire organization". Current paper intends to study integration of digital platforms in modern human resource and talent management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Talent management is a practice that aims to identify the "right" people and connect them with the "right" jobs, and advance their skills to facilitate realization of their supreme competences for achieving business goals. Talent Management especially essential for upper-level executives positions; to recruit and select the most inspired, educated, and talented individuals whose work may lead to organization prosperity (Miner, 1973 cited in Al Ariss et.al 2014).

Ingham (2006) states the concept of talent differs from one company to the next. Talent management (TM) administration must thoroughly analyze each of the following factors: talent definition, talent strategy, employee value position, and ability management skills. Ulrich and Smallwood (2012) gave full and clear analysis of what talent is and how it may be cultivated via succession, customization, and modeling, as well as recommendations for effective leadership investment. Scholars combined their results into the following formula:

Talent = competence + commitment + contribution

This formula can be interpreted as; talent is the sum of person's abilities, skills, experience and intelligence, which is competence and judgement, attitude, character and ability to learn.

DIGITALIZATION OF TALENT MANAGEMENT

Technologies give opportunities to make smarter decisions about talents based on data and people analytics platforms. Corporations can kickstart their transformational change to build momentum by embracing a bionic strategy that combines

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human and technical capabilities. Digitalization is not new a rule of the game for business executives anymore, but COVID-19 has made it more vital, as firms wish to maximize their agility, efficiency, and data-driven strategic planning. (Boston Consulting Group, 2021)

Today, hybrid working environment that includes both working in traditional offline offices and in remote working mode caused by COVID-19 requires changes in talent management. Changing HR eco system influences Talent Management cycles of companies all over the globe (Dhatariya, 2021). This study discusses integration of digital platforms in modern human resource and talent management.

METHODS

Present paper is grounded on secondary research that consisted of reviewing recent scholarly articles that were published from the year 2001-2021 on the topics of digitalization of talent management and features of employee platforms. Initially, market overview and general characteristics of modern talent management digital platforms were depicted. Furthermore, software features in the case of a certain vendor were discussed. Finally, comparison of employee management software suppliers and solutions was summarized.

RESULTS

There are varieties of different IT companies offering their platforms for personnel management. As shown in the Figure 1 the recruitment software market is estimated to reach the US\$ 3,095.8 mln by 2025 (Sagaya & Mujtaba, 2020).

Figure 1: Global recruitment software market size (2015–2025).

Source: Sagaya & Mujtaba (2020)

Talent management digital platforms perform numerous HR and talent management functions starting from job announcement to employee retention and motivation. Typical functions can include determining of skills and qualification gaps, employee goal and KPI setting, performance appraisal, feedback on performance, monitoring of learning programs for career development etc. For instance, talent management solutions such as Reviewsnap and Payscale enable potential applicants' skills and professional experience to be assessed in order to define training and development requirements (Dorasamy, 2021). Another example for such talent management cloud solutions offered by Oracle INSPIRE is presented in Figure 2.

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Figure 2: Employee Profile at Oracle's Talent Management Cloud

Source: Oracle (2019)

Oracle Performance Management Cloud Service (Performance Management) and Goal Management Cloud Service entirely automate performance and goal evaluation and monitoring, delivering instant value to executives, managers, and employees (Oracle, 2020). Figure 3 demonstrates features of Oracle HCM in terms of employee skill analysis. Oracle Recruiting Cloud resolves the typical issues of matching vacancy and employee skills to avoid skill gaps, locating the best talent, recruiting them efficiently, and training them successfully, and modernizes the whole recruitment process (ibid).

Figure 3: Skill analysis of Oracle HCM

Source: Oracle (2019)

Ganesh and Tyagi, (2021) carried out evaluation of different human resource management software that serves the primarily for human resources management and delivering training. These digital solutions have to be integrated to the different resource management processes. In their research, scholars compared eleven software products available in the market and suggested by the study respondents. People management procedures were chosen as the comparative attributes. The study depicted that HR

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software presented by ADP workforce served the mentioned main human resource features based on the comparison of required criteria.

Table 1: Comparative analysis of H.R.M software available in market

	Human resource	performance tracking, Compensation	Talent Management	Payroll Management	Recruiting	Cloud-based	Report & Analytics	Time, attendance, and scheduling	Training & management
Open H.R.	✓		✓	✓					
Adrenalin H.R.MS	✓	✓	✓		✓				
ADP Workforce	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
ADP Vantage HCM			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Bamboo H.R.	✓	✓			✓				
Suit H.R.				✓			✓	✓	✓
SAP ERP Core H.R.				✓			✓		
Microsoft Dynamics AX H.R.		✓			✓				
Microsoft Dynamics G.P. H.R.	✓			✓				✓	
SAP Success Factors	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓	✓
Oracle H.M.	✓		✓			✓	✓		

Source: Ganesh and Tyagi, (2021)

In post COVID-19 hybrid and remote environment, talent management ISs and platforms ought to be adapted to mobile phones to communicate and manage employees anytime anywhere. Talent management platforms require sufficient user friendliness for satisfactory user experience. There are other more features of HRIS and talent management platforms that must be considered. The purpose of this study is to identify the most important factors in selecting an efficient talent management platform.

CONCLUSION

The study gives the possibility for practical and theoretical implications. This study can be viewed as a contribution to a more comprehensive study of human resource information systems and digital employee platforms. Mostly on practical basis, this study will assist professionals in learning about the advantages or applications of digital platforms, and the results of this paper will be useful in determining the obstacles to HRIS adoption in order to be more informed. Furthermore, the research aims to underline that forward-thinking organizations implement a detailed plan for integration of human resource information systems and provide accurate data to decision-makers.

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